

The VI Cycle of Structured Dialogue Consultation

Introduction to the Final Reports

Introduction

After the 1st EU Youth conference of the VI Cycle of the Structured Dialogue, in Tallinn, Estonia, in October 2017, a pan-European consultation was launched through the National Working Groups (NWGs) and a European Working Group (EWG) of international non governmental youth organisations to engage with a broad youth population to have their say on the topics and questions raised during the 1st conference. The results of these consultations from across Europe have now been summarised into a series of 11 thematic reports, to be used as an input for participants at the 2nd EU Youth Conference to enable them to shape the Youth Goals. The diversity of the themes recognises the value of both dedicated youth policy, and cross-sectoral approaches to youth issues and young people, hence calling for mainstreaming of youth issues across diverse policy areas.

This document gives an outline of the consultation process, details of the numbers and profile of young people who took part, and outlines how the thematic reports were created.

This document, along with the the 11 thematic reports were authored by Dan Moxon and Ondrej Barta from The Pool of European Youth Researchers which is coordinated by the partnership between the European Commission and the Council of Europe in the field of Youth.

How did the consultation process work?

Following the 1st conference, a series of consultation questions and tools were created by the researchers, acting on behalf of the Structured Dialogue European Steering Committee. These were;

- **A set of broad consultation questions and guidance** - to provide a framework against which working groups could design their consultations and report their findings.
- **A set of standard survey questions** - for translation and use directly with young people in questionnaires.
- **A focus group guiding document** - to illustrate how the consultation questions could be explored within a focus group.

The questions and tools were based on the discussions “harvested” at the Tallinn conference. They were designed to enable consultations to focus directly on the themes arising from the 1st conference.

Working Groups used the consultation questions and tools to undertake consultation within their countries or in the case of the EWG, their organisational networks. Consultation processes were conducted independently and with full authority by each working group and therefore consultation processes used have differed, whilst still being guided by basic principles and questions outlined in the common documents.

Each working group was required to submit a report to the European Steering Committee and was optionally requested to supply an anonymised database of responses to the standard survey questions. Following this, based on the working group reports and the common survey data, the researchers created a series of 11 Thematic Reports. These reports were designed to reflect the major themes of discussion within the consultations, and to provide a tool for participants at the Youth Conference in Sofia in April 2018 to develop the youth goals.

How many young people took part and who were they?

Numbers of participants and working groups

A total of 29 national working group reports were received. This includes a report from every EU country except Greece, a report from the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, and two reports from Belgium (one from the French Community, one from the German community,

with no report received from the Flemish Community). One report was received from the EWG, combining consultation conducted by 10 international non governmental youth organisations.

Based on these reports an estimated **48,369** young people participated in the consultations in total.

- 20.6% took part in focus groups,
- 76.6% took part in surveys,
- 4.6% took part in other methods,
- Up to 1.8 % took part in more than one method.

The average number of participants engaged with by each participating working group who was 1612, this reduces to 1161, when Slovakia, who engaged with nearly 15,000 (sic!) young people is excluded from this calculation. The number of participants engaged with by each working group is shown in the graph below. It should be noted that many working groups included specific methods to speak directly with youth representatives, and some chose to focus primarily on this approach. To that effect, where working groups which engaged with smaller numbers of young people, it does not necessarily indicate a limited “reach” into the youth population, so much as a focus on youth representatives and the use of their links and organisational networks.

Reported number of participants by working group

Which countries did young people come from?

Each national working group collected responses from young people within their own countries, so participants are assumed to be residing within that country in some way. The European working group tracked residency of participants at the time of completion. Combining these figures, the countries of participants can be estimated.

95.6 % of participants were residing in EU countries and young people in all EU countries participated. Only 0.8% (387) participants were residing outside of EU countries, of these 0.6% (271) were in the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, with the remaining 0.2% (116) in Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Georgia, Iceland, Kosovo, Russia, Serbia, Turkey, Ukraine, Montenegro, Norway and Switzerland. The location of 3.6% (1724) of participants was not known. Full details are shown in the graph below.

Number of participants by country location

Controls were adopted to counter for the substantial variations between numbers of participating young people in each country when thematic reports were produced. Within the qualitative analysis of working group reports, documentation was not prioritised based upon number of responses. Within the common survey, statistical weighting were used to counteract for this imbalance (see below).

What were the backgrounds of young people who took part¹

Based on the numbers in the working groups' reports, It is estimated²;

- 42.0% of participants identify as male, 57.7 % identify as female, and at least 0.3% identify as another gender.
- 87.5% identify as heterosexual, at least 12.5% identify as homosexual, bisexual or another sexuality.
- At least 4.7% identify as having disability
- At least 9.5% identify as being part of minority ethnic group

Europe population estimates on disability, ethnicity and sexuality vary substantially, so proportions of participants within a representative sample of young people from these groups is hard to predict. However the figures above can be used, very crudely, to estimate within the consultation:

- Young men were under represented.
- An under representation of LGBTQI+ young people as a whole is likely to occur in the sample. However, there is not enough data to give an estimate on representation in subgroups, such as transgender young people.
- Young people with disabilities played a substantial role in the consultation but may still be may be partially under-represented in comparison to the size of pan-European population of disabled youth.
- Young people from minority ethnic groups seem to be rather accurately represented, even though the available comparison statistics vary as well as the interpretation of the term “minority ethnic group”.

Included in the figures above, a number of working groups also specifically targeted focus groups such as marginalised young people, and provided dedicated information on those groups. This included, but is not limited to, Roma young people, young people in social/youth care and young people in rural areas.

¹ This section is based on the data provided by working groups in their reports - as such, it will vary from calculations based on the common survey.

² Calculated as a percentage of total recorded and disclosed answers for each respective category.

The age profile of young people under 30 who participated is shown in the pie chart below³. In addition, it is known that a number of young people aged 30-35 also took part, however overall numbers of young people in this age bracket were not reported on across the whole consultation, and therefore no estimate is provided.

Estimated age profile of participants under 30

A number of working groups also consulted with experts, youth workers or policy makers and provided a direct response from working groups. Their responses were reported separately within the working group reports, and have been used to inform interpretation of responses from young people.

³ This is an estimate based on the National Reports.

How were the thematic reports written?

The thematic reports were written by the researchers to produce a short summary of the major areas of discussion within the consultations. The emphasis was on highlighting major trends, and areas of commonality rather than differences or contrasting priorities between working group reports. In general most working groups reported relatively consistent messages.

Text within the thematic reports is based on an analysis of working group reports to each of consultation questions. Each thematic report details which consultation questions have been used. Every attempt was made to include all the key messages within the working group reports whilst still keeping reports concise and usable for conference participants. To achieve this more concrete suggestions and recommendations were brought together into broader messages. Graphs and statistics in the reports were created using the consolidated data from the standard survey questions. (see below)

Information gathered through the harvesting tools was not used in the production of these reports, in order that they reflect the responses to the consultation exclusively.

Identification and selection of report themes

20 groups for discussion were proposed in an open space format during the Tallinn conference. Of these 20 groups 19 provided a record of their discussion to the researchers using the “harvesting tools”. The researchers undertook an analysis of harvesting tools during the Tallinn conference to look for overlap, similarity and connections within the detail of discussion. From this analysis, 14 distinct themes of discussion were identified. 13 of these were then used in the wider consultation with young people. The 14th theme (Coherence in youth policy) related to the technical drafting and implementation of the EU youth policy was not included in the consultation, as decided by the European Steering Committee, due to being limited to more technical aspects of EU youth policy.

These 13 consultation themes provided the basis for researchers to design the consultation questions and tools for the working groups. Consultation questions and tools aimed to reflect and continue the thematic discussions started within conference as closely as possible. Some themes required more than one consultation question to address effectively, giving a total of 16 consultation questions.

After the working group consultations were completed an initial analysis of working group reports was conducted by the researchers. This was done with an aim of identifying any areas of significant overlap between the responses to each question, or any significant gaps in data. No

significant gaps in data were identified. As well as the intended overlap between themes with two questions, two additional areas of overlap were identified:

- Questions on gender equality, inclusion of marginalised groups and migration had produced some overlap between responses in working group reports.
- Questions on Youth Spaces and Everyday Participation had produced some overlap between working group report responses.

Based on this analysis, the Steering Committee took the decision to combine some of the overlapping themes, leaving a final 11 themes;

- Education and Learning
- Employment
- Mental Health and Wellbeing
- Information, Dialogue and Difference
- Young People and the EU
- Gender Equality
- Inclusion (combining both inclusion of marginalised groups and inclusion of young migrants)
- Rural Areas
- Young people, the environment and sustainability
- European Youth Programmes and Youth Organisations
- Youth Spaces and Everyday Participation (combining the two named themes)

The thematic reports were then produced by the researchers for each of these themes using the data from the corresponding consultation questions, and cross referencing any remaining smaller areas of overlap as appropriate. Final names of themes were selected to be as neutral as possible, and are not intended to define the titles of youth goals, but provide working titles for delegates to work with.

Creation of common survey dataset

23 working groups supplied databases containing raw data from standardised survey questions. Out of these, 22 were in a suitable format for use to create a consolidated dataset and to conduct further analyses of responses received.

This consolidated dataset contained 29,482 responses of young people; after cleaning and further weighting adjustments of the sample, the resulting 25,734 respondents were analysed in a dataset limited to 11-34-year olds. The data set was weighted according to populations of

these young people in the respective countries, to prevent differences in numbers of consultation responses distorting the data. Further details of the common survey data can be found in the technical document.